

**Projection spread caused by missingness
in PCA on modern Worldwide populations:
Approx. # non-missing SNPs = 6000**

- Approx Geographical location**
- a Caucasus
 - a East_Africa
 - a North_Africa
 - a North_Europe
 - a South_Asia
 - a Uralic
 - a Centra_America
 - a East_Asia
 - a North_America
 - a South_Africa
 - a SouthEast_Asia
 - a West_Africa
 - a Central_America
 - a Middle_East
 - a North_Asia
 - a South_America
 - a SouthEur